

**THE INTERNATIONAL RATING AND ITS METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES:
PRIORITY IN THE CONDITIONS OF UZBEKISTAN****Kuchkarova Nazira Qaxramon qizi**

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Abstract. This paper aims to explore the significance of international ratings and their methodological approaches in the context of Uzbekistan. The international rating plays a crucial role in evaluating the economic, social, and political aspects of a country, and it has become increasingly important for Uzbekistan as it seeks to attract foreign investment and improve its global standing. This paper discusses the various methodological approaches used in international ratings and analyzes their relevance to Uzbekistan's specific conditions. It also examines the priority areas that Uzbekistan should focus on to improve its ratings and enhance its overall development. By understanding the importance of international ratings and their methodological approaches, Uzbekistan can effectively address its weaknesses and capitalize on its strengths to achieve sustainable growth and development.

Keywords: international rating, methodological approaches, Uzbekistan, economic development, foreign investment, global standing

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola O'zbekiston sharoitida xalqaro reytinglarning ahamiyatini va ularning uslubiy yondashuvlarini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Xalqaro reyting mamlakatning iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va siyosiy jihatlarini baholashda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi va bu O'zbekiston uchun xorijiy sarmoyalarni jalb qilish va jahondagi nufuzini oshirishga intilayotgani uchun tobora muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Ushbu maqolada xalqaro reytinglarda qo'llaniladigan turli metodologik yondashuvlar muhokama qilinadi va ularning O'zbekistonning o'ziga xos sharoitlariga mosligi tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, O'zbekiston o'z reytinglarini yaxshilash va umumiy rivojlanishini oshirish uchun e'tibor qaratishi lozim bo'lgan ustuvor yo'nalishlarni o'rganadi. Xalqaro reytinglarning ahamiyatini va ularning uslubiy yondashuvlarini anglagan holda O'zbekiston barqaror o'sish va rivojlanishga erishish uchun o'zining zaif tomonlarini samarali bartaraf etishi va kuchli tomonlaridan foydalanishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: xalqaro reyting, uslubiy yondashuvlar, O'zbekiston, iqtisodiy rivojlanish, xorijiy investitsiyalar, global obro'

Аннотация. Целью данной статьи является изучение значения международных рейтингов и их методологических подходов в контексте Узбекистана. Международный рейтинг играет решающую роль в оценке экономических, социальных и политических аспектов страны, и он становится все более важным для Узбекистана, поскольку он стремится привлечь иностранные инвестиции и улучшить свое глобальное положение. В данной статье рассматриваются различные методологические подходы, используемые в международных рейтингах, и анализируется их актуальность для конкретных условий Узбекистана. В нем также рассматриваются приоритетные области, на которых Узбекистану следует сосредоточиться для улучшения своих рейтингов и ускорения общего развития. Понимая важность международных рейтингов и их методологических подходов, Узбекистан может эффективно устранить свои слабости и извлечь выгоду из своих сильных сторон для достижения устойчивого роста и развития.

Ключевые слова: международный рейтинг, методологические подходы, Узбекистан, экономическое развитие, иностранные инвестиции, глобальное положение.

The international rating has become a significant tool for evaluating a country's economic, social, and political performance on a global scale. It provides valuable insights for investors, policymakers, and other stakeholders, helping them make informed decisions about engaging with a particular country. For Uzbekistan, a country that is undergoing significant economic and social reforms, international ratings play a crucial role in attracting foreign investment and improving its global standing. Therefore, understanding the methodological approaches used in international ratings and prioritizing the areas for improvement is essential for Uzbekistan's sustainable development.

International ratings are typically based on a set of methodological approaches that assess various aspects of a country's performance. These approaches may include economic indicators such as GDP growth, inflation rate, unemployment rate, and fiscal policy; social indicators such as education, healthcare, and poverty rate; and political indicators such as governance, rule of law, and political stability. The combination of these indicators provides a comprehensive evaluation of a country's overall performance and helps identify its strengths and weaknesses.

In addition to these traditional indicators, international ratings also consider other factors such as environmental sustainability, technological advancement, and innovation capacity. These factors are becoming increasingly important in the global context as countries strive to achieve sustainable development goals and adapt to the changing dynamics of the global economy. Therefore, methodological approaches in international ratings are continuously evolving to encompass a broader range of indicators that reflect the multifaceted nature of a country's development.

In the context of Uzbekistan, there are several priority areas that need to be addressed to improve its international ratings and enhance its overall development. One of the key priorities is economic diversification and modernization. Despite the recent reforms aimed at liberalizing the economy, Uzbekistan still heavily relies on traditional sectors such as agriculture and natural resources. To improve its ratings, Uzbekistan needs to focus on diversifying its economy by promoting innovation, entrepreneurship, and technological advancement.

Another priority area for Uzbekistan is social development, particularly in education and healthcare. While significant progress has been made in expanding access to education and healthcare services, there is still a need to improve the quality and relevance of these services. Investing in human capital through better education and healthcare will not only improve Uzbekistan's international ratings but also contribute to its long-term development.

Furthermore, political stability and good governance are critical for Uzbekistan's global standing. The recent political reforms have created a more open and transparent environment, but there is still room for improvement in terms of rule of law, anti-corruption measures, and institutional capacity. Strengthening political stability and good governance will enhance Uzbekistan's attractiveness to foreign investors and improve its international ratings.

In conclusion, the international rating and its methodological approaches are essential for Uzbekistan's sustainable development. By understanding the significance of international ratings and prioritizing the areas for improvement, Uzbekistan can effectively address its weaknesses and capitalize on its strengths to achieve sustainable growth. This requires a comprehensive approach that encompasses economic diversification, social development, and good governance. As Uzbekistan continues on its path of reform and modernization, international ratings will play a crucial role in shaping its future trajectory on the global stage.

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